

ACINO / D3.4

Application-centric routing and resource allocation algorithms for online operation

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Executive Summary

The outcomes of the design, development and evaluation of the ACINO application-aware resource allocation and optimization framework are summarized and reported, including also the developed algorithms that apply to both the IP and the optical network layers. The developed framework accommodates the application requirements of each demand in a dynamic way (i.e. online), as such demands (i.e. connection requests) arrive and depart at different times. This work builds on the allocation strategies and application aware policies presented in Deliverable D3.3, which are extended and refined.

The set of possible service requirements that accompany the service demands are first identified. These are: bandwidth, latency, availability, protection, and optical channel sharing (security). A network equipped with the ACINO algorithm must be able to satisfy all service requirements for each demand.

To satisfy the requests, an algorithmic framework has been developed and extensively tested on a reference network with simulations. The framework consists of three modules: IPP (IP layer provisioning), IP-OPT (IP layer optimization) and OPP (optical layer provisioning). IPP tries to accommodate the connection request by finding a path through the network only in the IP layer. IP-OPT moves existing IP connections to accommodate new requests, minimize the number of active IP equipment to save energy, and balance the IP link load. OPP sets up new optical connections. The framework thus calls IPP, IP-OPT, and OPP in a particular sequence to accommodate as many requests as possible, while minimizing energy consumption. The modules are implemented as Java code that runs as an algorithm for the Net2Plan open-source network simulator. The code can be run in a graphical user interface or in command line for batch runs.

On top of this framework, the ACINO algorithm was developed, which tries to satisfy all service requirements by allocating the appropriate amount of resources in IP and Optical domains. To investigate the effectiveness of the ACINO algorithm and the related framework, benchmark algorithms have been defined, in which the application awareness or/and the optimization process (implemented by IP-OPT) are deactivated. All benchmark algorithms still include optimal multi-layer allocation, same as the ACINO algorithm. The test scenarios involve an increasing number of traffic classes, each class having a distinctive set of requirements. The percentage of traffic classes and their service requirements are varied to get an insight into their impact on the algorithm performance. The performance is measured in several comparable quantities: the amount of blocked connection requests, the amount of requests whose requirements are not satisfied (referred to as SLA (Service-Level Agreement) violations), and the amount of network resources measured as the number of IP links. It is noted that in the case of ACINO, blocking can occur due to a lack of network resources to satisfy one or more service requirements (including the bandwidth), while in the benchmark application-unaware algorithms blocking is caused only by lack of bandwidth. Also, SLA violations are for established connections which do not satisfy the requirements. ACINO may thus have blocking but no SLA violations, while the application unaware benchmark algorithms may have both.

The numerical results demonstrate the advantage of the ACINO algorithm over the benchmark algorithms. ACINO serves successfully all the service requirements, achieving no SLA violations and, in most scenarios, very small blocking, while requiring almost the same number of network resources compared to the application unaware benchmark case. In the scenarios where ACINO shows some blocking (due mainly to inability to find resources that satisfy the service requirements), this blocking is found to be much lower compared to the sum of blocking and SLA violations in the application-unaware case. Therefore, compared to the application-unaware case, ACINO can provide more service level guarantees. In addition, this advantage of ACINO is achieved with the use of almost the same network resources. However, it is seen that the ACINO network requires setting up and tearing down optical connections more often, which in turn warrants an efficient ACINO controller. In addition, the role of IP-OPT optimization has been tested on both the ACINO and the application unaware network, showing significant saving in terms of network resources in both cases.

Finally, the software tool developed for the dynamic simulation is demonstrated in network planning scenarios. Here, the same framework and its software implementation are used to predict the impact of a hypothetical connection request and the effects of network component failures. The network operator can thus use the tool to prepare the network for future expected or unexpected events.

1 Overview of ACINO resource allocation framework

This section provides an overview of key design and implementation goals of the ACINO resource allocation framework. The framework functions are positioned at the heart of the ACINO orchestrator and are responsible for the optimum allocation of network resources at the Internet Protocol (IP) and Optical layers according to the received requests, which are treated based on their service requirements. The overall goal is to provide application aware allocation of the available resources.

In addition, this section describes the different versions of the framework, namely the online and offline versions and the implementation platform characteristics, built using the open Net2Plan simulation platform.

1.1 Main goals of ACINO application aware resource allocation framework

The development and evaluation of the application aware resource allocation framework is one of the key activities of ACINO project. The overall goals of the proposed framework are listed below:

- The framework must include a multi-layer resource optimization process that involves both the IP and optical layer resource allocation;
- Application aware features must be included with respect to the selection of the resources at the IP and the Optical layer separately;
- The framework must be compatible with the northbound interface requirements, thus dealing with specific set of service requirements according to an agreed list of attributes per service request;
- The framework must be implementable according to the defined orchestrator framework and be compatible with the IP and Optical controllers;
- A compatible simulation platform must be used in order to implement and evaluate the key features of the resource allocation framework before proceeding to integration with the orchestrator.

The aforementioned goals follow the implementation strategy defined in deliverable D3.3 [1]. Some more specific details are provided in the following paragraphs. The implementation details and the different options considered are described in sections 2 and 3.

Multi-layer resource optimization design goals

The adopted multi-layer optimization process considers first the optimum allocation of the existing IP resources and then the allocation of the optical resources. The rationale behind this approach is to make optimum use of the already available IP resources which are the main contributors in terms of cost and power consumption, before new optical layer connections and therefore additional IP resources are needed. When additional optical resources are introduced, the IP resources are re-optimised with the overall goal to maintain the optimum combination of IP and optical layer resources for serving the current requests (i.e. service requirements).

One of the key attributes of the multi-layer optimization process is the capability to periodically release unused resources, thus maintaining an optimal minimum number of them and reducing the overall energy consumption of the network. Another important attribute that is considered is the smooth and hitless migration from the current state to an optimized state in both IP and Optical layer, thus avoiding the interruption of services.

Goals of the added application awareness features

Separate routing and resource allocation decisions are implemented within the multi-layer optimization algorithms, according to the service requirements of each incoming request. This is actually the key differentiator of an application aware multi-layer resource allocation framework (i.e. the ACINO framework) and any common multi-layer framework that typically implements only one allocation strategy for any incoming request. In the ACINO allocation framework, a different service requirement-based decision is defined for each one of the supported service requirements. These include so far the following:

- a. **Latency awareness:** In this case the allocated end-to-end route is examined in terms of the targeted overall delay, which may include just the propagation delay or in addition any processing delay in the nodes. A new optical link is requested if none of the existing IP routes can meet this requirement.
- b. **Protection:** only IP protection is assumed. (Optical protection can be implemented if needed at the physical layer and relates mostly with the infrastructure properties, thus affecting the availability of the connections). In this case, each request that asks for protection is assigned two disjoint paths in the IP topology. The paths are disjoint in that they have no common IP links, no common IP routers except the ingress and egress, and no common fibres traversed by the lightpaths implementing the IP links. These requirements protect the applications against fibre cuts, IP router failures, and IP port failures. In addition, the traffic can be recovered quickly, in the IP layer using a mechanism such as IP/MPLS Fast Reroute in under 50 ms. Both the working and protective paths should also satisfy any additional service requirement.
- c. **Availability:** In this case each optical link in the network is assigned with a metric that denotes the overall availability (or equally the probability of failure). Practically this metric can be based on link statistics typically obtained by operators and the provision of optical 1+1 protection.
- d. **WDM class/Security:** Certain applications may request data transfer over dedicated WDM channels, thus avoiding the aggregation with data from other applications. This is primarily requested for security reasons or for business cases in which the end-to-end services are totally managed by the customers (e.g. leased line services)

The bandwidth requirement is a common feature in all cases and therefore is treated by the overall multi-layer resource allocation process. The ACINO resource allocation framework can handle any request that combines the aforementioned service requirements, or even with no particular service requirement (i.e. best effort case). When multiple service requirements are requested then each one is treated separately and a common decision that satisfies all of them is made. Finally, the framework is designed to be open to

any new type of service requirement that could be introduced in addition to those presented above and are currently implemented.

Compatibility with north-bound interface requirements

The framework has been designed and implemented as a stand-alone platform and in the absence of the overall orchestrator. However, the design considers the compatibility with north-bound interfaces and uses a mechanism that pushes the application requests with certain service requirements to the framework, in turn requesting the allocation of the required network resources. For this reason, the traffic generation functions that are required in order to evaluate the ACINO resource allocation framework have been implemented as a separate module and an additional layer in the simulation platform. This allows requests to be pushed independently to the resource allocation modules emulating the orchestrator environment in which requests will be pushed by the north bound interface. Additionally, the framework implements the feedback signals to the north-bound interface, indicating the possible blocking of requests, due to a lack of available resources.

Compatibility with the ACINO Orchestrator framework

The final implementation goal of the ACINO resource allocation framework is to be included in the ACINO orchestrator. This primarily relates with the interfaces of the resource allocation framework with the ONOS controller. Therefore, the key modules of the resource allocation framework are implemented independently of the input and output interfaces. This allows any future updates in the algorithms to be easily implemented without affecting the overall ACINO orchestrator. The compatibility of the resource allocation framework interfaces with ONOS is examined in work package WP4, task T4.2 and will be reported in deliverable D4.2. That implementation is performed in parallel and independently of the work presented here (work package WP3, task T3.4).

Development and evaluation environment for the ACINO resource allocation framework

The defined multi-layer and application-aware resource allocation framework must be implemented and evaluated before proceeding to the integration with the orchestrator. Beyond the actual development of the framework modules, functions and algorithmic solutions, the important goal of this activity is to define:

- a. which features must be and are worth to be included in the framework modules’;
- b. what are the optimum values in the multi-layer framework functions in terms of overall performance and added complexity;
- c. how the ACINO resource allocation framework will be compared with other non-application aware solutions;
- d. how the overall complexity can be reduced and at what cost.

These are key design aspects that affect the final implementation and integration of the proposed framework in the orchestrator as well as its upgradability. For this reason, the Net2Plan open simulation platform chosen for the development of the ACINO framework and the related studies. The reasons for selecting this platform and the offered capabilities for our studies are described in subsection 1.3.

1.2 Online and offline versions

The ACINO framework has been designed in order primarily to support online operation. Its final objective is to be part of the orchestrator and handle connection requests that are randomly received by the north bound interface in real time. A secondary objective is to use the ACINO resource allocation framework as a planning module, in order to estimate network performance characteristics and needs of resources under different conditions. The latter version is considered as a planning tool for the operator, enabling him to perform network planning and resource utilization studies, as well as run ‘what-if’ scenarios, in an effort to examine the tolerances of the network with respect to different application aware service requests.

The selected simulation platform allowed the design of a modular framework that can be easily converted from an online tool to an offline version. All the defined modules (see section 2) and the functions included in them, deal with specific tasks and can be considered as stand-alone modules in the orchestrator. Different types of optimization algorithms can be selected in each module according to the required optimization target and the type of applications to be handled. Certain functions can also be enabled or disabled according to the required functionality versus the added complexity that needs to be achieved.

The same types of modules, functions and algorithms are also included in the online version of the ACINO framework (i.e. the ACINO planning tool), thus achieving exactly the same functionality as the online version. What changes is only the overlay traffic generation framework and the way that the requests are inserted for processing. A significant addition in the offline version is the cost evaluation module that implements the adopted cost models for the IP and Optical layers and provides a cost estimation of a snapshot of the network by considering the active connections and types of allocated resources. Details about the cost model and the implementation of the cost evaluation module are provided in deliverable D2.3.

1.3 The Net2Plan simulation platform

The Net2Plan multi-layer network simulation platform [2] is chosen with the main purpose to develop and evaluate the key features of the resource allocation framework before proceeding to the integration with the orchestrator. The platform is also used to examine extreme networking cases and scenarios, identifying the operating limits and the scalability of the framework. We justify this decision in more detail by describing properties of Net2Plan useful to the ACINO project, as follows:

- Net2Plan code is open source. One of the requirements for the ACINO orchestrator is that it is open source. Thus, since the Net2Plan code is open source, and ACINO code is released as open source as well, the optimization part of the orchestrator can be said to be open source.
- Net2Plan code is free in monetary terms, and as such its use in ACINO requires no financial resources.
- User support has been found to be satisfactory. In particular, there is a detailed user guide, a Javadoc documentation listing the data structures and Java methods used in the code. In addition, we have established a good working relationship with the authors of Net2Plan, who have so far responded very quickly to our inquiries and bug reports.

- Net2Plan features a useful graphical use interface (GUI). Visualizing the network provides additional value to the simulation platform for two reasons. First, while the optimization code is developed, the developer can observe the effect of the optimization code, such as verify that the paths through the network are valid and that the input data is correctly read. Second, the network designer or operator can observe the interesting properties of the optimized network, such as various statistics, as well as manipulate network elements (routes, links, nodes) and observe the effects of such manipulation. The Net2Plan GUI is shown in Figure 1.1 below with some basic elements highlighted.

Figure 1.1: Net2Plan graphical user interface.

- Net2Plan has a command line interface (CLI). Other than the visualization, the CLI has the same functionality as the GUI, and the results of the optimization runs can then be loaded into the GUI for further inspection. The main advantage of the CLI is that it allows for multiple (batch) runs, without the need to change the input parameter for every run once the CLI batch file has been created.
- Net2Plan has a special module that allows for an exchange of data with ONOS. The way this is accomplished is described in more detail in Deliverable D4.2.
- The code and data structures defined in Net2Plan provide a reference for other tasks in ACINO. Developers of other tasks can then develop their code with a common view of a network, which reduces the effort needed to coordinate the tasks.
- The Net2Plan engine can take, for each connection request, service requirements defined in the ACINO project as input.

- Net2Plan has a well-developed subsystem for generating statistics about the network. Some of the statistics code is already built in, and we have added more features to examine our output network models (these statistics are shown in latter sections).
- Many of the routines commonly used in network optimization, such as shortest paths and sorting, are included in Net2Plan and can be readily used. The authors of Net2Plan are experienced in network optimization, so the quality of their routines can be expected to be high. This reduces optimization code development time.

2 ACINO resource allocation framework, modules and information flow

This section presents the ACINO resource allocation and optimization framework that is implemented and examined in this deliverable. The framework features have been studied previously in task T3.3, and multiple options have been investigated during the development phase in task T3.4. This section provides further details and remarks about the implemented multi-layer framework modules, as well as the application aware features that are considered for the service requirements of the demands.

2.1 Description of the ACINO multi-layer resource allocation framework

The ACINO multi-layer resource allocation framework considers first the allocation of a request using the existing resources in the IP layer and, if this is not possible, then a new lightpath (i.e. IP link) is generated to accommodate this request. The main principle behind this is based on maximizing the utilization of the existing costly IP resources before a new resource is requested. A critical addition in the framework is the optimization algorithm which can run either after the allocation in the IP layer or after a new lightpath is assigned (leading to a new IP link being generated) or after both phases. This optimization algorithm essentially targets the reallocation of resources according to a certain target. Most commonly the target is to minimize the overall use of resources for the given requests in the network.

The consortium has examined various options for the implementation of the framework and settled for the one that is described in the following steps and depicted in Figure 2.1:

1. When a request arrives, try first to accommodate it using the existing IP links. This is the job of the IP provisioning (IPP) module. The IPP module maintains an updated status of the network resources and identifies the optimum IP route to the destination according to the service requirements of the received request. This module does not interact with other established connections.
2. If necessary resources are available in the IP domain, the information is sent to the controllers to reserve them and establish the connection. If not, the IP optimization (IP-OPT) module is called. The IP-OPT module can also optionally run after a number n of successful allocations in order to re-optimize resources.
3. The IP-OPT module optimizes the allocation of the IP connections based on the existing optical layer resources. The purpose of this module is on one hand to identify the available resources and possibly accommodate a request that failed during the IPP module process and on the other hand to minimize the number of active connections, thus identifying and (if requested) removing the unutilised (i.e. empty) ones. This module does not interact with the optical layer resources.
4. If the IP-OPT module is capable of providing the IP resources for the request, then the information is sent to the controllers to establish the connection. If not, the request is passed to the multi-layer optimization (ML-OPT) process in order to generate a new optical lightpath and provide the requested IP link.

5. The ML-OPT process is composed of the Optical Provisioning (OPP) module and the IP-OPT module. First, depending on to the received request, a number of valid optical paths are suggested by the OPP module. These are also listed according to an optimization target (e.g. shortest path). Then the IP-OPT module runs for the first m of the listed solutions, trying to minimize the overall IP connections given the new IP connection due to the new lightpath. The lightpath that provides the best result (i.e. less IP resources) is selected and the information is passed to the controllers for establishing the connection.

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the multi-layer resource allocation framework.

The proposed multi-layer resource allocation framework provides a clear separation between the allocation and optimization processes, as well as a structured way for how the IP and Optical layer resources are handled. The framework is designed to be modular and easily modified according to the added complexity that we need to have. For example, the IP-OPT module can be turned off, allowing only the IP and Optical provisioning functions to be executed. This offers very fast resource allocations but without any added optimization. Alternatively, the IP-OPT module can be skipped when only the IPP or the OPP module have run, allowing the resource optimization to be run only when IPP fails or when a new optical path is set-up, respectively. The same modularity is also present within each module. One may select among different optimization algorithms and decision polices with respect to routing and path identification. Details about the implemented algorithms and the different options are provided in section 3.

2.2 Framework modules

The modules described in the following paragraphs are the building blocks of the ACINO resource allocation framework. Each module is dealing with specific functions and can be implemented using different approaches (i.e. algorithms). Therefore, the modules are implemented as separate entities in the ACINO framework, allowing any alternative algorithmic approach or update to be easily incorporated in future versions.

2.2.1 IPP Module (IP provisioning module)

This module Provides optimum allocation of a request as an IP connection (an LSP) in the IP layer, using only available resources and taking into consideration the service requirements and the network resource availability. The module does not change or move established connections. It deals only with the allocation of the input request. It can implement different routing algorithms with different optimization targets, as long as they do not violate the service requirements.

2.2.2 IP-OPT Module (IP optimization module)

This module re-optimizes all the existing IP connections. If required it includes in its calculations the requested IP connection that could not be provisioned by the IPP module. The IP-OPT module considers a fixed IP topology (i.e. it causes no changes in the optical lightpaths). The basis for the re-optimization is to re-arrange the IP connections either with the goal to optimally accommodate the new service request in the IP layer or in general to minimize the number of active IP links. IP-OPT considers changes that can be made in sequential steps without interrupting the established connections (i.e. make before break mode). This sequence of steps is provided as output to the controllers. Finally, IP-OPT is capable to identify empty IP-links and ask for their termination, thus providing energy savings.

2.2.3 OPP Module (Optical layer provisioning module)

The goal of the OPP module is to identify the optimum new connection in the optical layer to allocate a new service request. The optical connection can be a new end-to-end lightpath or the extension of an existing path. The final goal is to establish an optical lightpath that allows an end-to-end IP link to be formed for the requested connection, obeying to its service requirements. This module is capable of providing various possible optical paths and listing them according to a certain optimization target. The IP-OPT functions can be used if required in order to determine the best one. The OPP module does not consider modifying the existing optical links.

2.2.4 ML-OPT Module (Multi-Layer optimization module)

The role of an ML-OPT module is to change the established optical links of the IP connections, to reach an optimum according to optimization target: typically, it will minimize the number of required optical links for a given number of IP connections. Essentially, an ML-OPT module includes the IP-OPT functions that are executed for any new optical layer topology change that is proposed. It is important that the ML-OPT provides the migration steps from the old to the new (optimum) configurations in the optical and IP layers, on a make before break mode (also called hitless mode).

REMARK: In the delivered version of the ACINO resource allocation, the ML-OPT module is implemented with the combination of the OPP and IP-OPT and according to the description in step 5 in subsection 2.1. This has been agreed by the consortium due to the increased implementation complexity that is required in order to develop a full ML-OPT module that reshuffles the optical layer connections. In addition, such added complexity is not expected to have a significant contribution to the overall performance of the ACINO optimization process since a significant optimization level is achieved at the IP layer. Moreover, practically, the migration process would be a rather time consuming due to many changes in the optical domain.

2.3 Application aware features

The resource allocation framework structure presented refers simply and in general to an efficient multi-layer optimization framework. In order to implement the ACINO application-aware features, specific optimization algorithms and decision policies have been implemented in all three modules: IPP, OPP and IP-OPT. Therefore, for each of the incoming request, the service requirements are first examined and the related application-aware policies are implemented. If no service requirements are defined for the incoming requests, then these are treated as 'best effort' cases and the ACINO framework operates as an application-unaware multi-layer resource optimization framework (this is required for the benchmarking case of the performance studies). The application-unaware multi-layer framework maintains the functions for the optimum bandwidth allocation of the requested connections, as well as the optimization processes in the IP and Optical layer.

2.3.1 Latency awareness

Latency relates to the propagation delay and optionally the processing delay in IP nodes. Optical nodes introduce no latency. Latency-aware routing algorithms are implemented in all three modules. In addition, the framework supports multiple latency values, thus allowing for example classes of services with very strict latency requirements, others with average requirements and others with no specific requirements.

2.3.2 Availability

Actual link and node failure statistics are used in order to determine the probability of a failure in the network. A service with high-availability requirements is allocated over secure paths with a reduced overall probability of failure. This requires the execution of a specific routing algorithm in the IPP and OPP modules, which considers the availability metrics of the IP network based on the network statistics.

2.3.3 IP Protection

For applications with IP protection service requirement, the disjoint IP paths algorithm is executed for the simultaneous identification of paths following separate optical links in any part of the end-to-end route. This is done exclusively in the IPP module and, if required, is repeated in the IP-OPT module. In case other service requirements are also requested, then the latency and availability algorithms precede and provide the pool of candidate links for selecting the possible disjoint paths.

2.3.4 WDM class (Security)

Certain applications may request data transfer over dedicated WDM channels, thus avoiding the aggregation with data from other applications. This is primarily requested for security reasons or for business cases in which the end-to-end services are totally managed by the customers (e.g. leased line services). The provisioning of WDM classes is done in the OPP module and the separation is examined also in the IPP module. The optimization processes in IP-OPT distinguish the applications in different WDM classes and apply their features separately in both.

3 Algorithms

In this section, we describe in detail the resource allocation algorithms and the traffic generator necessary to evaluate them. The algorithms have been designed to implement the specific functions required by the modules described in section 2.2.

3.1 Algorithms implementing the framework modules

The modules exploit the concept of Auxiliary Graphs (AGs), firstly formalized in [3], and extends the multi-layer Auxiliary Graph construction methodology proposed in [4] to provide application-awareness for each service request by taking into consideration multiple application requirements. Moreover, the algorithms have a modular design, i.e., they can be extended to consider further application requirements than the ones considered in this Deliverable.

As a general model, we assume that a service request r is represented by a $r(s, d, b, l, a, p)$ tuple, where s and d are the identifiers of the *source* and *destination* IP/MPLS routers for the service request, b is the requested bandwidth, l the maximum tolerable end-to-end latency, a the minimum tolerable end-to-end path availability and p specifies whether the application traffic associated to the service request must be protected or not. The network must then provide connectivity to the application requesting the service by computing one (or, in case of protection, a couple of) end-to-end path that satisfies b, l, a, p (i.e., the application requirements) at the same time, i.e., one (or a couple of) *application-aware path*.

In the first subsection, we describe the Auxiliary Graph Model that is used by the algorithms implementing the modules described in section 2.2. Then, the implementation of modules IPP, IP-OPT, OPP and ML-OPT is described, each in its own subsection.

3.1.1 Auxiliary Graph Model

The Auxiliary Graph model we propose for computing application-aware paths for each service request is based on the IP layer network topology. To construct it, all the IP nodes (i.e., IP/MPLS routers) are firstly added to the AG. Then, two different types of edges can also be added, i.e., *existing* and *potential* lightpath edges:

- An *existing lightpath* edge is added if a lightpath has been previously established in the optical layer between two IP nodes. An existing lightpath already carries some network traffic and is associated to an IP adjacency.
- A *potential lightpath* edge represents whether a transparent lightpath (and, consequently, an IP adjacency) could be established between two IP nodes on the Auxiliary Graph, given the current state of network resources in the optical layer (e.g. wavelengths).

This approach allows to construct a simple single-layer graph (i.e., the Auxiliary Graph) for each service request, instead of dealing with multi-layer graphs, that takes into consideration *i)* the multi-layer (IP and optical) nature of the physical network and *ii)* its state in terms of available resources. Such Auxiliary Graph can be manipulated to provide application-awareness to service requests. Once the Auxiliary Graph is

constructed, it is possible to compute a proper path for the service request by running a path selection algorithm on it. An example is shown in Figure 3.1.

The Auxiliary Graph model is adopted for the design of the algorithms implementing the IPP and OPP framework modules described in section 2.2. Specifically, depending on the framework module that needs to be implemented, the information used to construct the Auxiliary Graph changes, as is presented in sections 3.1.2 to 3.1.5.

Figure 3.1: Simple example of Auxiliary Graph and chosen path for a service request.

3.1.2 IPP

The primary function of the IPP Module (IP Provisioning Module) is finding one (or two, in case of protection) application-aware path(s) in the IP layer, i.e., by only using the available resources in the network. The flow diagram of the IPP resource allocation algorithm is shown in Figure 3.2.

The parameters considered in Figure 3.2 are reported and briefly described in the following table.

Table 3-1. Summary of parameters.

Parameter	Description
s	Source node for the service request
d	Destination node for the service request
b	Minimum bandwidth for the service request
l	Maximum end-to-end latency for the service request
a	Minimum end-to-end availability for the service request
p	Need for IP protection ($p = true$) or not ($p = false$)
B_{lp}	Available bandwidth for the considered lightpath
L_{path}	Latency of the computed path
A_{path}	Availability for the computed path

Figure 3.2: IPP Algorithm flow diagram.

The algorithm attempts to find an application-aware path that reuses existing lightpaths, i.e., reuses already-existing IP adjacencies in the IP layer.

To do so, an Auxiliary Graph including only *existing lightpath edges* is constructed (*Auxiliary Graph construction* phase). Among these edges, the ones not meeting b , i.e., with available bandwidth $B_{ip} < b$, are pruned. Such an Auxiliary Graph ensures that the remaining edges all meet the bandwidth application requirement for the service request. It should be noted that the Auxiliary Graph only deals with the actual information at the IP layer.

After constructing the Auxiliary Graph, the *path selection phase* is performed. The K_{ip} -Shortest Path (SP) algorithm between s and d is run on it. The weight chosen for each existing lightpath edge is its physical length. K_{ip} -SP gives as output up to K_{ip} candidate paths, all meeting the bandwidth b application requirement. Among such candidate paths, the algorithm prunes the ones with latency $L_{path} > l$ and with availability $A_{path} < a$. Note the path latency and availability are calculated by:

$$L_{path} = \sum_{node \in path} L_{node} + \sum_{link \in path} L_{link}$$

where L_{node} (L_{link}) is the latency added by a traversed IP/optical node (link), while

$$A_{path} = \prod_{node \in path} A_{node} \cdot \prod_{link \in path} A_{link}$$

where A_{node} (A_{link}) is the availability of a traversed IP/optical nodes (links) [5].

At this stage, all the remaining candidate paths meet the b, l, a application requirements. The last application requirement that must be considered is the protection p . If the service request does not require any protection, i.e., if $p = false$, the first path in the list of candidate paths (i.e., the shortest) is chosen as *application-aware path* for the service request r , and the requested bandwidth b is allocated over the traversed existing lightpaths. Conversely, if the traffic associated to the service request needs to be protected at the IP layer ($p = true$), the first node/link disjoint path couple is selected. The algorithm first check for disjointness at the IP layer, then verifies whether disjointness occurs at the optical layer. If not, the couple is discarded and the next one is considered. Once an IP/optical node/link disjoint path couple is found, the first path of the couple is labelled as *application-aware working path*, while the second one is labelled as *application-aware backup path* for the service request r . The requested bandwidth b is then allocated over the traversed existing lightpaths for both the working and the backup path. In case no solution can be found, a *NULL* marker is output.

It is important to note how the input value K_{ip} must be carefully chosen, since it influences the number of candidate paths that are investigated by the IPP algorithm. A high value for K_{ip} allows to explore a higher number of candidate paths and to more likely find an application-aware path, but the computational time is higher due to the execution of the K_{ip} -SP algorithm with higher K_{ip} . Conversely, a low value for K_{ip} allows to save computational time at the expense of neglecting some paths that could be chosen as application-aware paths.

Moreover, the algorithm could easily be extended to consider further application requirements in a modular way. Application requirements, in fact, can *i)* modify the Auxiliary Graph construction phase, by pruning links, and/or *ii)* modify the path selection phase, by pruning paths or by using different policies for the path selection. As a simple example, an end-to-end optical encryption e application requirement could also be considered. $e = true$ would mean that the application requires end-to-end optical encryption. In the Auxiliary Graph construction phase, other than pruning all the existing lightpaths not meeting the b application requirement, all the existing lightpaths but encrypted end-to-end lightpaths would also be pruned. However, we leave the implementation and evaluation of such extension as future work.

3.1.3 IP-OPT

The IP-OPT module optimizes the IP layer usage without breaking the application awareness.

This module takes as input a list of the current connections established in the IP layer in the network (i.e. IP routes), together with the service requirements that each connection satisfies. In addition, the algorithm takes some input parameters, described below. The output is a new set of IP connections¹.

The algorithm begins by sorting the list of input IP routes. There are four ways to sort: initial, random, increasing and decreasing. With initial, the list is left as it was presented to IP-OPT. With random, the list is permuted randomly. With increasing, the routes are sorted in a non-decreasing order by the amount of traffic (in Gb/s) that each route carries. Decreasing order is equivalent, where the order is non-increasing. With the increasing and decreasing options, we do not care how the sorting ties are broken and we leave them to the implementation.

Next, the IP routes in the ordered list are processed one at a time. For each route, the algorithm finds up to K alternative routes, where K is an input parameter set by the user. Each of the up to K routes must satisfy the same service requirements as the original route. In other words, if there exists a route R for a connection request E with a set of service requirements S , and R changes to R' , then R' must satisfy S . Note that the change assumes that no other change in the network is occurring at the same time.

To find the up to K alternative routes, the algorithm constructs a graph containing all the IP routers and the IP links with sufficient spare capacity to carry the requested traffic. The link weights are all set to one. On this graph, IP-OPT runs the well-known K shortest paths algorithm.

Once the up to K alternative routes have been found, the algorithm makes the decision to choose one route or retain the existing one. To make the decision, we define a cost function (described below). For each possible change of a route R to R' , we compare $\text{cost}(R)$ to $\text{cost}(R')$, and only accept the change if it reduces the cost, i.e. if $\text{cost}(R) < \text{cost}(R')$. Among all (up to K) potential changes, a change with the minimum cost is selected. If there are multiple changes with the same cost, we leave the tie breaking to the implementation. Note this is a local optimization approach, in the sense that the solution found converges to a local optimum. However, since the connections over the network continuously change, a later call of IP-OPT will break out of this local optimum.

The cost function tries to satisfy three main objectives, ordered by importance: (i) that no traffic requests are unsatisfied, (ii) that the number of IP links is minimum, and (iii) that the utilization of the links is balanced. This is done using the following formula:

$$C_0 \sum_{\text{unrouted requests}} \text{requested_bandwidth} + C_1 \times \text{number_of_links} + C_2 \sum_{\text{link}} \text{link_traffic}^2 \quad \text{with} \quad C_2 \ll C_1 \ll C_0$$

Each term in the formula is designed to satisfy each of the above criteria, and in the same order. The cost is calculated in a way that guarantees that the values of the three terms never overlap, i.e. the minimum of

¹ The IP connections here use explicit (source-based), rather than hop-by-hop, routing. This kind of routing is more akin to MPLS routing than OSPF, but we use "IP" to emphasize that we are dealing with the electronic layer, and leave the choice of the routing protocol to the real network implementation.

the first term is higher than the maximum of the second term. Note that the second term aims to reduce the number of active IP links. The inactive links found as a result of the optimization can be turned off and the energy required to maintain them saved.

An important consideration in the algorithm selection for IP-OPT was that the changes suggested should be implemented on the network in a hitless way. In other words, implementing the optimized network cannot result in service interruptions; otherwise each call to IP-OPT, which may occur after every connection request, may cause a service interruption. In order to facilitate such hitless operation, a list of changes is maintained in the order that they can be implemented, and only the changes that are possible without affecting other connections are considered. More specifically, after a change from route R to route R' is selected, it is added to the ordered list. The list does not shrink until IP-OPT has finished. When the final, improved, state is determined, these changes are implementable on the network in the order specified without any service interruption.

In addition, the algorithm maintains another invariant, which is that the implementation of the list of IP route changes on a real network can be interrupted at any time: the changes are performed one by one, and after each, the network is left in a working state with all services intact. If a change cannot be implemented, e.g. due to a failure in the network, the remaining changes can be abandoned without causing service interruption.

To help maintain the invariants of hitless and service-preserving operation, we chose not to change the routes that have a backup route, i.e. the routes with a protection service requirement. To change two routes in an optimal way would add complexity to the algorithm. To see this, note that changing a route that has a backup route requires finding two new routes with mutually disjoint paths. We have found this to be computationally difficult. In addition, the change from the original pair of routes to the alternative ones is difficult to do in a hitless way. We leave this problem for future work.

3.1.4 OPP

The primary function of the OPP Module (Optical Provisioning Module) is to establish new optical connections (i.e., lightpaths) in the optical network and to find application-aware paths for the connection requests by using such lightpaths. The application-aware paths can be *i)* end-to-end lightpaths or *ii)* lightpaths that extend existing IP routes. The flow diagram for the OPP resource allocation algorithm is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: OPP Algorithm flow diagram.

The algorithm flow diagram is very similar to the IPP algorithm flow diagram described in section 3.1.2. The only difference between the OPP and IPP algorithms is in the Auxiliary Graph construction phase. In fact, the OPP algorithm, as the IPP algorithm, creates an Auxiliary Graph that includes all the *existing lightpath edges* and prunes the existing lightpaths not meeting the b application requirement. However, OPP also augments the Auxiliary Graph by adding *potential lightpath edges*.

To add potential lightpath edges, all the possible IP node pairs on the Auxiliary Graph are considered. A potential lightpath edge between a node pair is added only if *i)* no usable existing lightpath edge already exists between those nodes in the current Auxiliary Graph, and *ii)* there are enough optical resources to establish it. To check whether there are enough optical resources to establish such potential lightpath, the K_{wdm} -Shortest Path (SP) First-Fit (FF) routing and wavelength assignment algorithm [6] between the considered node pair is run on the optical topology. K_{wdm} indicates the number of shortest paths that are explored in the optical layer.

This way, in the path selection phase, that exactly works as in the IPP algorithm: we increase the chance of finding an application-aware path at the expense of having to set up one or more new lightpaths in the network. If at least one (or a couple of) application-aware path is selected (i.e., it satisfies all the application

requirements), the chosen wavelengths are allocated for the traversed potential lightpath edges, their states are changed from *potential* to *existing* and, lastly, the requested bandwidth b is allocated over all the traversed lightpaths. It is important to note how K_{wdm} must be carefully chosen, since it influences the chance of finding an optical path with enough resources to be associated to a potential lightpath edge. A high value for K_{wdm} allows to explore more optical paths at the expense of increasing the computational time. Conversely, a low value for K_{wdm} saves computational time but risks to neglect optical paths that could be associated to the potential lightpath.

3.1.5 ML-OPT

This module is the multi-layer optimizer. It functions as a linked combination of modules OPP and IP-OPT. IP-OPT is used to help OPP select the optimum IP routes for the connection requests. It takes as input the current network, complete with the optical and IP layer nodes and links, the connections in each layer, and any connection requests that have not yet been accommodated. The output is a new network that accommodates some or all of the connection requests, and the set of actions needed to transform the input network to the output. We describe more algorithmic details below.

First, the OPP module sets up new IP links (connections) and adds IP connections. The resulting network is passed to the IP-OPT module. IP-OPT then optimizes the IP connections as described in section 3.1.3, which results in a new network. In doing so, IP-OPT both accommodates any new requests and simultaneously optimizes the IP network.

Even more specifically, after constructing a new optical and IP network, OPP tries each possible candidate IP route by using IP-OPT as the decision maker. Thus, for each possible route R to satisfy a connection request, IP-OPT produces an optimized network with an active route R . Among all such networks, i.e. among all candidate routes, the one with the minimum network cost (received from IP-OPT) is selected. If there are multiple such minimum cost networks, the tie breaking is dealt with by the code implementation.

IP-OPT also produces a list of changes to the existing IP connections that supports uninterrupted network services. In the context of IP-OPT, these changes are to the IP connections in the network that OPP passed to IP-OPT. In such a network, some of the IP links, and consequently some of the IP connections, do not exist in the real network yet. ML-OPT thus outputs the IP links that need to be set up, the IP connections that need to be set up, and the changes to the IP connections.

3.2 Traffic generator algorithm

The traffic generator generates a time sequence of connection requests. Each connection request is characterized by its start and stop time and thus by its duration, its service requirements, and origin and destination IP routers. We now describe how these quantities are computed to generate the connection requests.

To generate the connection requests, the generator takes as input the input *traffic matrix*, which is a matrix of average traffic rates (in Gb/s) for each pair of IP routers in the network. The traffic generator aims to maintain this traffic matrix, i.e. the input traffic rate for each pair of IP routers.

Another input to the generator are the traffic classes, where each class has all service requirements specified. Note that this specification may include, for a particular traffic class and service requirement, “don’t care”, i.e. the service requirement is not specified and thus does not have to be accommodated by the optimization algorithms. Each traffic class has a percentage, which is an input to the generator. Of course, the sum of traffic class percentages must be 100%.

For a given traffic class, the service requirements are the same as the service requirements noted in section 2.3, with the addition of bandwidth as follows. The traffic class specifies the minimum and the maximum bandwidth that a connection request may have. The connection requests in a particular class will have a bandwidth between the minimum and the maximum chosen randomly, using a normal distribution.

The traffic generator generates a time sequence of connection requests independently between the classes. In other words, the time sequence of connection requests for a particular class is generated independent of the other classes as if there were T traffic generators for T traffic classes.

In a time sequence, the generator computes the start time of a connection request as follows. The start time is the time of the arrival of the previous connection request in the class plus the *interarrival time*. For the first connection request, the previous connection request time is set to zero. The interarrival time is an exponentially distributed random variable, where the distribution parameter (λ) equals $1/\text{average_interarrival_time}$. This is computed as:

$$\text{average_interarrival_time} = (\text{average_duration} \times \text{average_bandwidth}) / (\text{traffic_load})$$

where the quantities are as follows:

- *average_duration* is an input parameter
- *average_bandwidth* is the average between the minimum and maximum bandwidth for the traffic class
- *traffic_load* is the traffic class percentage multiplied by the traffic matrix entry for a specific IP router pair (origin, destination).

It should be noted that *traffic_load* is specific to a router pair for which the connection request is generated. The order in which the router pairs are processed is left to the implementation and is in fact arbitrary. This is because the generator creates a sequence of connection requests independently for each router pair. To clarify, at time zero the generator schedules one future connection request for each router pair for each traffic class. Then, at each connection request start time, a new request is scheduled between the same pair of routers in the same traffic class using the formulae shown above.

Finally, for each request, the duration time is an exponentially distributed random variable, where the distribution parameter (λ) equals $1/\text{average_duration}$. The request stop time then equals the start time plus the duration time. The generator thus functions as a Poisson birth/death process with the above-mentioned average rates.

4 Evaluation of the online ACINO resource allocation framework

This section presents the evaluation results of the ACINO resource allocation framework and provides the required comparisons with a non-application aware solution. The overall evaluation procedure is explained in subsection 4.1. Then the simulation platform, topology details and the user interface are described in subsection 4.2. The following two subsections present the evaluation results and the key finding of the studies: in subsection 4.3, different types of application classes and combinations of classes are evaluated, and the relative performance results are presented and commented. Then, in subsection 4.4, the effects of fluctuating traffic and the related resource usage are examined and also commented.

4.1 Description of the evaluation procedure

The ACINO application-aware multi-layer framework is capable of allocating demands and reserving the required resources according to the individual service requirements of each demand. In addition, the implemented resource optimization procedures are targeting the maximization of the successfully established application-aware connections and typically the minimization of the overall utilized resources. The typical non-application-aware multi-layer resource allocation solutions deal with the optimization issue but any decision taken applies to all traffic demands, since these are not separated into classes with different attributes (i.e. service requirements). Therefore, the evaluation of the ACINO resource allocation framework and its comparison to other multi-layer resource allocation solutions is not a straightforward procedure that can be simply based on typical performance metrics like blocking probability and resource utilization.

In the first some key comparison remarks adopted hereafter are highlighted. Then follows a subsection in which the evaluation procedure is defined and presented.

4.1.1 Key comparison remarks

In order to have a fair comparison of the added value that is introduced with the use of ACINO, when compared to a non-ACINO solution, the benchmark non-application aware resource allocation framework must be properly defined. This non-ACINO (i.e. non application-aware) framework should maintain all the multi-layer processes and the related optimization functions defined for ACINO, as described in subsection 2.1. The main difference is that none of the application-centric policies apply during the IP and Optical resource provisioning functions and the optimization processes. The ACINO multi-layer allocation and optimization framework has some unique attributes with respect to other multi-layer approaches that mainly relate to how the optical provisioning and IP optimization features are efficiently combined, as well as the capabilities offered by the modular design of the framework. The attributes of the multi-layer design are not highlighted with the proposed comparison, as the focus is primarily on the added value of application-awareness which is the main scope of ACINO project. In addition, the non-ACINO framework implements the application demands for separate WDM allocation and IP protection.

Another important parameter for a fair comparison is the generation of the same traffic pattern for both the cases that are compared. For this reason, the traffic generator uses the same seed number and most importantly is implemented as a separate module that is commonly used in both cases. During the

evaluation, the generator produces the defined traffic pattern with the required application classes (according to the scenario under study) for both the ACINO and non-ACINO cases. In order to achieve the functionality described in the previous paragraph for the non-ACINO case, the framework code has been modified accordingly so that the service requirements related only with the latency and availability features of the incoming traffic events are ignored. This is equivalent to a generator that generates only best effort type of traffic and, if required, maintains traffic aggregation over separate WDM channels and IP protection.

It should be noted that the benchmark algorithm, although reasonably simpler than ACINO, is fairly sophisticated. More specifically, the algorithm allocates resources across both layers, and the connection requests that consume the resources are dynamic as opposed to static. In addition, the algorithm must be implementable on a real network equipped with an orchestrator, so path computation runtimes must be moderate so that the application can be assigned resources as quickly as possible; this requirement also drives our preference for IP (IPP is tried first) to IP-and-optical allocation.

4.1.2 Evaluation metrics

A new metric is introduced for the evaluation of the non-application aware case. This is the “service request violation” metric, which denotes the ratio of the connections that at any point in time do not meet any of their service requirements, to the total number of requested connections. As mentioned above, the same traffic demands are generated for both ACINO and non-ACINO cases, and they contain specific service requirements even if these are not considered in the allocation of resources when the non-ACINO case is evaluated. Since in the non-ACINO case the allocation is done without considering any specific policies, there is a possibility that some of the established demands are allocated over paths that would have never been selected in the ACINO case, in order to avoid the violation of service requirements.

The “connection establishment blocking” is also a metric of key importance, in particular for the ACINO case. ACINO avoids any service request violation; however, when no network resources are available to establish a connection with the agreed service requirements then the connection is blocked. Therefore, blocking in ACINO case denotes the lack of resources to meet the application requests.

Some key remarks with respect to the above metrics are listed below:

- The ACINO case has always zero service request violation.
- For a given number of demands, if the number of resources in IP and Optical layer is large then also a zero or at least a very small service request violation is expected for the non-ACINO case.
- For the non-ACINO case, service request violation metric is expected to increase, as the number of application sensitive demands increase for a given number of available resources.
- Once the available resources are limited then the connection establishment blocking metric for ACINO case is expected to increase.
- The connection establishment blocking metric will always be equal or higher than that in the non-ACINO case due to the additional restrictions in the use of resources imposed by the ACINO application policies.

The aforementioned metrics are evaluated and presented both as a percentage of the total number of requested connections and as a percentage of the total requested bandwidth of the connections. The latter is important in order to have a more accurate estimate in terms of the overall resources when applications with different bandwidth requirements are considered (e.g. 1Gb/s-10Gb/s applications and aggregated 10Gb/s-100Gb/s applications).

4.1.3 Evaluation options and procedures

As mentioned above, the two general cases that are evaluated and compared are the following:

- a. The **application-aware framework**, which allocates the requested connections so that their service requirements are met; otherwise the connection is blocked.
- b. The **non application-aware framework**, which maintains the same multi-layer resource allocation structure as in the previous case but ignores specific service requirements, during the resource allocation process.

Each of these cases can be further split into three subcases, with respect to the implemented optimization algorithms and the level of optimization level that is reached.

1. Simple allocation of resources: Here the framework structure is followed for any new connection request, however the IP and Optical layer optimization functions are skipped. This means that the resources are optimally allocated when a request arrives, but they are not further re-optimized as the demands change in the network.
2. Optimized allocation of resources: In this case the multi-layer optimization process and application related polices are activated. The resources are re-optimized in order to accommodate more connection requests and maximize the use of network resources. Here, all the proposed changes during re-optimization should apply in a hitless manner, (i.e. without disturbing the existing connections).
3. Global optimization of resources: This case includes the use of optimization algorithms and processes that achieve the best resource utilization. All connections are reshuffled until the optimum combination is identified. This is a non-practical approach as a migration path from the current network status to the globally optimized status is not guaranteed.

The combination of the above give 6 cases which are shown in Figure 4.1. The ACINO framework is represented by the combination case a-2, whereas the non-ACINO framework by the combination b-2. The ‘simple allocation’ case requires more network resources than the optimized case. However its implementation is simpler and has a faster execution time. It can be used in order to evaluate the benefits of the optimization process in terms of utilized resources. The ‘global optimization’ case is not a practical case but it is significant in order to identify the (almost) best allocation of resources for benchmarking purposes. Ideally, the target for ACINO framework is to achieve a much better use of resources compared to the simple allocation case and be very close to the global optimization case.

Figure 4.1: Evaluation options for the application and non-application aware cases.

According to the cases shown in Figure 4.1, a number of comparisons are possible in order to evaluate both the multi-layer optimization framework and the added benefits of the ACINO application-aware approach:

- B1-B2-B3 comparison:** A simple multi-layer resource allocation approach without considering any service requirements (B1) allows the optimum allocation of IP resources and the simultaneous management of optical resources according to the increasing or decreasing IP demands. The proposed multi-layer optimization approach (B2) can dynamically optimize the network resources, maximizing the available IP bandwidth for new requests while minimizing the generation of new optical links (i.e. the activation of new IP ports). Thus, B2 is expected to require less IP resources than B1.
- B2-A1 comparison:** Although in B2 the resources are optimized, the service requirements are not taken into consideration. A simple application-aware resource allocation solution (A1) allows all the service requirements of the established connections to be met. However, the added restrictions in terms of allocation are expected to lead to an increased number of required resources compared to the B2 case.
- A1-A2-B2 comparison:** In order to meet the requested service requirements and optimize the use of available resources, the ACINO resource allocation framework and the corresponding application-aware policies were adopted and implemented in A2 case. This case is expected to reduce the number or

required resources (IP ports and optical links) compared to A1. The final target is to achieve a similar number of resources as in case B2, at the expense of additional processing complexity in the optical layer since optical paths have to be adjusted according to the incoming service requirement requests.

- **A3-A2 comparison:** Finally the global optimization process (A3) will show the (close to) ideal number of required resources needed. This comparison can be used in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed application-aware resource allocation framework in terms of resource utilization.

REMARK: The obtained results presented in section 4.3 are focusing on the comparison of A2 and B2 cases. For the practical scenarios a comparison with A1 case is performed too. These are the key comparisons in order to demonstrate the efficiency of the application-awareness concept by the ACINO framework under different service requirement scenarios, which is the main goal of ACINO. Therefore, although the algorithms for all 6 cases have been developed, the efficiency of the multi-layer resource allocation framework (i.e. B2-B1) and the comparison to the global optimization case (A2-B2-A3) are not examined in this deliverable. Such additional comparisons require extra effort and computational time and will be presented in the final deliverable issued in M30 of the project.

4.2 Description of the implemented ACINO simulation platform

The simulation platform is based on Net2Plan, which has a particular philosophy for multi-layer networking. Consequently, although the code developers and users of Net2Plan are given freedom in choosing their views of the network, algorithms, parameters and data structures, the simulation platform has to adhere to the principles of Net2Plan. The alternative is to completely overhaul Net2Plan. Since Net2Plan is completely open source, this is theoretically possible but invalidates the choice of Net2Plan as the basis for simulation (WP3) and resource allocation (WP4).

In the following three subsections we describe the characteristics of the simulation platform.

4.2.1 Simulation platform structure

In simulations, our network consists of three layers:

- the optical layer holds information relevant to the optical layer in the real network: the fibre-links, occupied and free optical channels and lightpaths.
- the IP (electronic) layer has the IP links and routes, and tracks the amount of traffic on each link and route.
- the traffic matrix layer has the traffic matrix and the percentage for each traffic class (for an explanation of traffic classes, see section 3.2)

Each layer in Net2Plan has its own links and routes. In addition, our simulations use two more Net2Plan elements that each layer has, which are protection segments and demands. Protection segments are backup routes to be used in case of failures, which have a reserved capacity set by the algorithm or the GUI user. Demands are equivalent to connection requests in the IP layer, and are characterized by bandwidth and service requests. Demands also exist in the optical layer; here they are needed to implement routes in the optical layer, which represent lightpaths in Net2Plan.

This brings us to the relationship between the abovementioned elements as follows: in each layer, there exist demands, which are accommodated by one or more routes, which cross one or more links. Thus, a route cannot exist without a “parent” demand, and must cross one or more links. In the traffic matrix layer, we only use demands (to store connection requests), while the other elements are not needed.

Finally, Net2Plan has nodes that are not layer-specific, i.e. each node is present in all layers. Consequently, there is no provision to simulate IP routers separately from optical switches or other real-world boxes. In addition, Net2Plan has no provision for node ports². We get around this problem by tagging network nodes equipped with IP routers with a Net2Plan *attribute*, specifically setting the *IPNode* attribute to true. This attribute is then read by our code, e.g. to establish IP links between IP nodes in the simulated network. In general, each element (link, node, route, etc) in Net2Plan can have one or more attributes, that can store any information. This information can be read and processed by the simulation code.

4.2.2 Implemented topology details

In this subsection, some properties of the network modelled in our simulation are described, by layer:

Optical layer

Figure 4.2 shows the topology in the optical layer, derived from the reference network. The links in the figure represent fibre links and the nodes optical switches. In the simulations, we use only one fibre per fibre-link. The topology is input to the simulation and does not change until the simulation finishes.

Figure 4.2. The simulated network optical topology.

Table 4-1 shows some statistics that Net2Plans shows once the topology is loaded into the GUI. *Capacity installed* here means the number of spectrum slots in a fibre. In our model network, we assume that 12.5

² In the simulation we do not track or limit the number of ports in either the optical or the IP layer. We will simulate ports in WP4 and describe how ports are simulated in the relevant Deliverable.

Ghz spectrum slots are available. Consequently, if we want to simulate WDM channels over the conventional grid with 50 Ghz spectrum slots, we will assign four slots to a channel ($4 \times 12.5 \text{ GHz} = 50 \text{ GHz}$).

Table 4-1. Net2Plan statistics for the optical layer.

Number of nodes	30
Number of links	112
Node out-degree (max, min, avg)	5, 3, 3.733
All links are bidirectional (yes/no)	Yes
Layer diameter (hops, km, ms)	7, 944.000, 4.72
Capacity installed: total	35840.000
Capacity installed: average per link	320.000
Capacity installed (limited capacity links): total	35840.000
Capacity installed (limited capacity links): average per link	320.000

IP (electronic) layer

The IP layer consists of fourteen routers, which are collocated with the optical switches. In our simulations, the network starts with no pre-established IP links. Figure 4.3 thus shows an IP topology at the end of a simulation. During the course of the simulation, the IP topology may change as links are added and removed.

Figure 4.3 An example of the simulated network IP topology.

Table 4-2 shows the statistics for the IP layer at the end of a simulation. *Capacity installed* is expressed in Gb/s. Net2Plan shows the network topology diameter in kilometres and milliseconds: in our algorithm, we assign to each IP link a length equal to the length of the lightpath implementing the link. These values are necessary to compute the latency that an application running over a particular IP route experiences.

Table 4-2. An example of Net2Plan statistics for the IP layer.

Number of nodes	30
Number of links	118
Node out-degree (max, min, avg)	19, 0, 3.933
All links are bidirectional (yes/no)	Yes
Layer diameter (hops, km, ms)	3, 1062.000, 5.31
Capacity installed: total	43600.000
Capacity installed: average per link	369.492
Capacity installed (limited capacity links): total	43600.000
Capacity installed (limited capacity links): average per link	369.492

Traffic matrix layer

As noted earlier, this layer holds only the traffic matrix and the traffic class percentages. The traffic classes are defined for each node (IP router) pair and stored in the traffic matrix layer as Net2Plan demand attributes. The traffic class percentages also define the number of traffic classes. For example, an attribute “*trafficClassPercentage = 0.1,0.9*” means that there are two classes, where the first has 10% and the second 90% of the traffic. Although this can be defined per node pair, we defined the same classes and percentages for each node pair.

4.2.3 User interface structure and usage

In the GUI, the user first loads the network topology with the layers described previously. Then in the Execution Controller tab, there are two tabs: the first, Event Generator, contains the parameters for generating and removing connection requests (IP layer demands in Net2Plan). The second, Provisioning algorithm, contains the parameters for the algorithm that accommodates the connection requests. The parameters are typed in, chosen using a drop-down menu or marked in a check box. If the user enters a parameter out of range, a warning is displayed and the simulation is prevented from starting until the user error is corrected.

The Net2Plan code and data structures provision for such parameters to be defined, but the definitions are part of ACINO code and not of Net2Plan (website) distribution. We now discuss the parameters, shown in Table 4-3 and Table 4-4 in some detail. The values shown are the defaults for the simulation, and the text

descriptions are shown to the GUI user. Many of the descriptions are sufficient to explain the meaning of the parameter, so we focus on additional explanations.

Table 4-3. Net2Plan Event Generator parameters.

InterarrivalTimeMultiplierArray	1,1,1,1	For the first 1/ArraySize events, average interarrival times will be multiplied by the first factor, etc.
averageHoldingTimeInSec	1000	Average connection duration (in seconds) (1/mu)
averageInterarrivalTimeInSec	1	Average connection interarrival time (in seconds) (1/lambda)
maxBandwidthArrayInGbps	100	Possible maximum bandwidth for the connection requests (Gbps)
maxLatencyArrayInMs	5,100	Possible maximum tolerated latencies for the connection requests (in milliseconds)
minAvailabilityArray	90,99	Possible minimum tolerated availabilities for the connection requests (in %)
minBandwidthArrayInGbps	10	Possible minimum bandwidth for the connection requests (in Gbps)
numConnectionsSimulation	100	Number of connections to finish the simulation (a negative or zero value means no limit)
numConnectionsTransitory	-1	Number of connections to finish the transitory (a negative or zero value means no transitory)
protection	1	0 for unprotected class, 1 for protected class
randomSeed	1	Seed for the random generator (-1 means random)
simulationModel	longRun	Simulation model: 'longRun' (connections are established and released), 'incrementalModel' (connections are never released)
trafficLayer	ELECTRONIC	Layer containing traffic demands
wdmClass	0,1	Each wdmClass will be routed independently in the WDM layer

InterarrivalTimeMultiplierArray – the user specifies how traffic will change over time in. While connection requests arrive and leave as a Poisson process, this array is concerned with long-term traffic fluctuations. This is covered in more detail in section 4.4.

The following parameters are specific to the traffic class: *maxBandwidthArrayInGbps*, *minAvailabilityArray*, *maxLatencyArrayInMs*, *minBandwidthArrayInGbps*, *protection*. In each box, the user specifies the value for each class in order, separated by a comma. If the number of classes is greater than the number of values in a box, the values are assigned in a round-robin fashion, i.e. for classes number N and V values the $(N \bmod V)^{\text{th}}$ parameter is selected. This saves time when entering the parameters if several classes e.g. have the same level of protection. Recall that the classes are defined in the traffic matrix.

Table 4-4. Net2Plan provisioning algorithm parameters.

IPOPT_file	C:\...\bin\ip_opt_simple_aa.class	IPOPT algorithm (default ip_opt_simple_aa)
IPOPT_classname	ip_opt_simple_aa	Algorithm class name
IPOPT_parameters	K=5, demandOrder=initial,seed=-1	Algorithm parameters
IPOPT_run	-1	Run IPOPT after this many succesful IPP runs (-1 to disable)
IgnoreAvailabilityandLatency	false	If checked, availability and latency will be ignored when finding paths.
K_ipLayer	50	Maximum number of candidate paths to setup IP routes
K_wdmLayer	5	Maximum number of candidate paths to setup lightpaths
TRxAvailableBitrates	10, 100, 200, 400	Array of transceiver binary rates (in Gbps)
TRxReach	3000, 2000, 1000, 500	Array of transceiver reach (in km)
TRxSlots	2, 3, 4, 6	Array of spectral slots needed for respective bitrate
costModel	CostModel.xls	Excel file with the cost model values
costModelFrequency	-1	How often to calculate the cost (-1 to disable)
flexgridPolicy	maxBW	Transceiver selection policy: mix is maxBW for wdmClass > 0, minBW otherwise
oppAlgorithm	pathSelectionPolicy	OPP algorithm
pathSelectionPolicy	minLat	Path selection policy
removeEmptyIPLinks	true	Whether to remove unused IP links
removeFrequency	0	Try to remove IP links after that many IP_OPT calls (if 0 try even if IP_OPT wasn't called)
routerDelay	0.0	router processing delay (ms) per router per packet
wdmShortestPathType	km	Shortest path type in the optical layer: hops, or km

For the *IP_OPT* parameters, the user selects a file containing the Java class file and the Java class therein, and then selects the parameters for that particular algorithm (these parameters also have default values and explanation like in the main Provisioning algorithm tab).

IgnoreAvailabilityandLatency – this Boolean parameter is what distinguishes an ACINO algorithm simulation from a “best effort” run (as discussed in section 4.1.3).

flexgridPolicy (maxBW, minBW, mix) – this parameter denotes what kind of transceiver is assigned to a particular connection. When setting up an optical connection, *maxBW* will, for example, use the largest transceiver available (i.e. with the highest rate in Gb/s). With *mix*, it is possible to assign the largest transceivers (to aggregate traffic), except for the WDM traffic classes denoted with a non-positive number (defined in the Event Generator), which get the smallest transceivers available. This *mix* policy thus allows for a simulation of situations where the customer is requesting a leased line and is given an entire optical channel regardless of the traffic that will be sent on the channel, but with the smallest line rate. The other optical connections in the network aggregate traffic from multiple customers and are thus given the largest transceivers.

oppAlgorithm (pathSelectionPolicy, IPOPTcost) – to choose a path in the IP network, the OPP algorithm can use two options: The first one is to choose the path based on some properties like the length (see below); the second one is to run IP_OPT to select the best path. With the second option, *IPOPTcost* chooses the path that would have the minimum cost in an optimized (as opposed to the current as constructed by OPP) IP network.

pathSelectionPolicy (minLat, maxLat, maxDisLat, minAvResBand, maxAvResBand, minResBand, maxResBand, minPathWiseResBand, maxPathWiseResBand) – these are the criteria to select among the candidate paths. In a simulation, the same policy applies to both layers. The table below explains each policy:

Table 4-5. Path selection policy parameter options.

<i>minLat</i>	Choose the latency shortest path
<i>maxLat</i>	Choose the latency longest path
<i>maxDisLat</i>	Choose the latency longest path that is disjoint with the latency shortest path
<i>minAvResBand</i>	Choose the path that in average (i.e., according to the number of hops) leads to the minimum residual bandwidth on the links
<i>maxAvResBand</i>	Choose the path that in average (i.e., according to the number of hops) leads to the maximum residual bandwidth on the links
<i>minResBand</i>	Choose the residual bandwidth shortest path <=> Minimum residual bandwidth path
<i>maxResBand</i>	Choose the residual bandwidth longer path <=> Maximum residual bandwidth path
<i>minPathWiseResBand</i>	Find the path with highest bottleneck among the candidate paths
<i>maxPathWiseResBand</i>	Find the path with lowest bottleneck among the candidate paths

routerDelay – this parameter applies to all IP routers in the network.

4.3 Evaluation of different application demands and types

In this section we evaluate the efficiency of application awareness in terms of resource allocation. Different application scenarios are considered for evaluating the specific effects for each application type. The application-aware optimised ACINO approach is also compared to other multi-layer schemes including: an application-unaware scheme, a non-optimized application-aware scheme and an ideal optimization scheme.

4.3.1 Overview of application evaluation studies and scenarios

In this section, we first conduct a study of the impact that different input traffic makes on the output network design and the services that can be supported. The goal is to find the service requirement value ranges that are applicable to our network model. For example, we want to know how much blocking traffic with a specified latency will cause as we increase the percentage of such traffic in the network. Based on this study, we define a realistic traffic mix, i.e. realistic service requirements to examine the difference between the ACINO approach and the other schemes.

To that end, the study shown is based on two-class traffic first, and then expanded to three classes. For both the two- and three-class inputs, we examine the impact of latency, availability, WDM class and protection service requirements, both individually and combined. The evaluation metrics used are outlined in section 4.1.

Finally, in section 4.3.3 we run realistic scenarios with six traffic classes.

4.3.2 Evaluation studies – Results and discussions

2-classes: {Latency} – {Best effort}

For the two classes case, the input connection requests all have between 10 and 100 Gb/s bandwidth. The latency-sensitive class requires 6ms latency. We use conventional WDM in the optical layer, so the number of spectrum slots is four per optical connection. The transceivers are 100 Gb/s with a reach of 2000 km. The removal frequency is 10. Router delay is 0.5 ms per packet per router. We run the simulation for 10000 connection requests, which Figure 4.5 shows to be a sufficient number. The parameters are thus the same as in Table 4-3 and Table 4-4, except for the differences shown in Table 4-6 and Table 4-7. Note that the minimum and maximum bandwidth are 9.99 and 99.99 as opposed to 10 and 100, to avoid the well-known inherent problems with floating point calculations in the computer.

Table 4-6. Changed parameters from Table 4-3.

maxBandwidthArrayInGbps	99.99	Possible maximum bandwidth for the connection requests (in Gbps)
maxLatencyArrayInMs	6,99999	Possible maximum tolerated latencies for the connection requests (in milliseconds)
minAvailabilityArray	0	Possible minimum tolerated availabilities for the connection requests (in %)
minBandwidthArrayInGbps	9.99	Possible minimum bandwidth for the connection requests (in Gbps)
numConnectionsSimulation	10000	Number of connections to finish the simulation (a negative or zero value means no limit)
protection	0	0 for unprotected class, 1 for protected class
wdmClass	1	Each wdmClass will be routed independently in the WDM layer

Table 4-7. Changed parameters from Table 4-4.

TRxAvailableBitrates	100	Array of transceiver binary rates (in Gbps)
TRxReach	2000	Array of transceiver reach (in km)
TRxSlots	4	Array of spectral slots needed for respective bitrate
costModel	CostModel.xls	Excel file with the cost model values
costModelFrequency	1	How often to calculate the cost (-1 to disable)
flexgridPolicy	minBW	Transceiver selection policy: mix is maxBW for wdmClass > 0, minBW otherwise
oppAlgorithm	pathSelectionPolicy	OPP algorithm
pathSelectionPolicy	minLat	Path selection policy
removeFrequency	10	Try to remove IP links after that many IP_OPT calls (if 0 try even if IP_OPT wasn't called)
routerDelay	0.5	router processing delay (ms) per router per packet

We now discuss the numeric results. For all runs in with the above settings, there is zero blocking for both the ACINO and the application unaware algorithm. The difference is that for the application-unaware case, some paths are longer than the latency permitted by the service requirements. We count the number and the bandwidth of the connection requests whose service agreements are violated. More precisely, we track the fraction of all such violated connection requests over all the requests that arrived over the course of the simulation; the same is done for the requests' bandwidth. We denote the violations as "SLA violations" and show the fractions in Figure 4.4 below. Note that the percentage of latency-sensitive traffic is varied, to show the effect of the amount of sensitive traffic on SLA violations.

Figure 4.4. Percentage of SLA violations as a function of the percentage of latency-sensitive traffic for the application-unaware case.

Next, we show the total number of IP links (lightpaths) over the course of the simulation when the latency-sensitive traffic is 10%, 50% and 90%. We also show the amount of IP links (lightpaths) that ACINO and application unaware add (by using the OPP algorithm). The figures below do not show these quantities after every connection request, but after every 100th. This is to avoid making the lines too jagged to be able to see the trends.

Figure 4.5. (left) Total number of IP links in the network. (right) Cumulative number of IP links (lightpaths) added to the network by OPP, shown as an extra needed for ACINO compared to the application unaware case.

On the left side of Figure 4.5, the number of IP links stabilizes after about 5000 connection requests. Then, the number hovers around 200, i.e. +/- cca 30 IP links, in both ACINO and the app-unaware case. ACINO and

app-unaware thus use the same number of IP links, and this number does not change significantly with the percentage of latency-sensitive traffic.

On the right, we see that ACINO adds more IP links, except for a period when there is 10% of latency-sensitive traffic (and even then only about 2% less). The number of extra IP links grows as the percentage of latency-sensitive traffic is increased. This suggests that an ACINO-equipped network will take longer to accommodate the traffic, because setting up an IP link (lightpath) is a relatively slow operation. In addition, to maintain the circa 200 IP links active (the same as the app-unaware network) ACINO has to remove them more frequently. As a result, the more dynamic ACINO network needs an orchestrator to handle the frequent turn on/turn off operations without disrupting the running services. In return, ACINO can accommodate the latency service requirement and offer a more sophisticated service to the customer.

Next, we vary the service latency requirement together with the router delay. The results are shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6. The blocking and SLA violations results for varying latency and router delays. Blocking is zero for all cases in app-unaware. SLA violations are zero for all cases in ACINO.

At the left side of the figures, the values for ACINO blocking and application-unaware SLA violations are quite high, which is understandable given that a 4ms latency is quite low for our model network. In the middle, the plot suggests that the network could support 6ms of latency with 1ms router delays for less than 1% blocking, while the application-unaware case would have no blocking but high violations. Beyond 6ms latency, ACINO has no more blocking while the application-unaware continues to violate service requirements until about 10ms of latency. Going from 30% to 50% of sensitive traffic increases blockings and violations by about 1.75 times.

2-classes: {Latency, Availability} – {Best effort}

We now add availability to the latency requirement for the sensitive class. First, we set the availability to 99.5% and vary the amount of sensitive traffic. To achieve this in simulation, the *minAvailabilityArray* parameter is set to “99.5, 0”. Figure 4.7 below shows the results. We only show the SLA violations because blocking is zero for the app-unaware case, while in ACINO there is only 0 to 0.1% blocking.

Figure 4.7. Percentage of SLA violations as a function of the percentage of latency-and-availability-sensitive traffic.

Next, we investigate the impact of a variable availability service requirement. Figure 4.8 below shows the results.

Figure 4.8 shows a trade-off: ACINO, while not causing any violations, blocks some connection requests at very high availability. The app-unaware case will not block, but cause a significant percentage of connections to not satisfy the service requirements.

Figure 4.8. Impact of varied availability.

Next, we show the results for three classes. Here, there are two classes with specified service requirements, and one without. The two sensitive traffic classes split their percentages of total traffic equally, so if the percentage of sensitive traffic is P , the two sensitive classes will each be $0.5P$ of the total traffic.

3-Classes: {Latency, Availability} – {Latency} – {Best effort}

For this case we set latency to 6ms and router delay to 0.5ms. Availability is 99.5%. These service requirements are kept for the other 3-class cases.

3-Classes: {Latency, Availability, WDM-class} – {Latency} – {Best effort}

The traffic class with the specified latency and availability is in its own WDM class (as described in section 2.3.4), while the other two traffic classes belong to their own WDM class. To achieve this, the parameter *wdmClass* is set to “1,2,2”.

3-Classes: {Latency, Availability, IP-protection} – {Latency} – {Best effort}

The first class features IP protection (as described in section 2.3.3), in addition to latency and availability. The *protection* parameter must be set to “1, 0, 0”.

3-Classes: {Latency, Availability, Low-Bandwidth} – {Latency} – {Best effort}

So far, all connection requests have been between 10 and 100 Gb/s. We now investigate the effect of smaller requests. To that end, the first class has requests between 1 and 10 Gb/s. Since the traffic generator must still maintain the input traffic matrix, these small requests arrive more frequently.

Figure 4.9. SLA violations for the different 2- and 3-class scenarios.

Figure 4.10. SLA violations for the different 2- and 3-class scenarios, to show the percentage of violating traffic out of the amount of sensitive traffic.

Most of the scenarios shown above cause no or very little (less than 0.1%) percent blocking for both app-unaware and ACINO. However, when IP protection is introduced, there is blocking. We believe that this is

caused by a) the current inability of IP-OPT to move protected IP connections and b) the additional constraints that finding disjoint paths for protection imposes. We leave addressing a) for future work.

In Figure 4.11 below, we show that even with blocking, ACINO achieves a better result than the app-unaware algorithm.

Figure 4.11. Comparison of application-unaware and ACINO service requirement accommodation for the 3-class scenario with protection.

More precisely, note first that ACINO respects all service requirements. Next, while blocking is about twice as large for ACINO, compared to the amount of sensitive traffic that the app-unaware algorithm does not serve (violations plus blocking), ACINO blocking is low.

4.3.3 Realistic scenarios – Results and discussions

So far, the input traffic has had a small number of classes, which do not necessarily correspond to traffic classes that would be expected in a real network. We now increase the number of traffic classes. The goal here is two-fold: to make the traffic mix more realistic, and to investigate how the ACINO algorithm performs compared to the application-unaware one. Table 4-8 below shows the input traffic specifications. We first define three broad types of traffic: data centre, cloud services and best effort, each with a specified requested bandwidth and availability. Then we refine these types by specifying several types of services in each, with their own distinctive service requirements. Each of these services has a particular percentage of total traffic, which in turn allows us to define two scenarios: today and future. Today, most traffic is best effort with only a small percentage of traffic belonging to highly constrained cloud services. In addition, a significant amount of traffic is between data centres. In the future, this ratio is expected to change, as services become more constrained, so more services will require availability and IP protection.

Table 4-8. Realistic scenarios and service requirements for the scenario traffic.

Traffic type	Traffic type serv. requirements	Service-specific requirements	WDM class	Scenario 1: Today	Scenario 2: Future
Data center	10-100Gb/s, Availability 99.5%	Latency 10ms	1	20%	40%
		-	1	20%	10%
Cloud services	1-10Gb/s	Latency 10ms	3	4%	10%
		Latency 10ms, IP protection	3	4%	10%
		Latency 6ms, IP protection	2	2%	10%
Best effort	10-100Gb/s	-	3	50%	20%
				100%	100%

Next, we present simulation results for the ACINO and application-unaware cases.

Table 4-9. Results for the realistic scenario.

IP-OPT ON	application-unaware				ACINO			
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW
TODAY	0.5%	0.1%	8.8%	13.8%	1.9%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW
FUTURE	0.6%	0.2%	8.2%	17.4%	2.6%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW

ACINO results in some blocking, which, similarly to the case of three classes (section 4.3.2), we believe is due to the severe constraint of IP protection and the suboptimal handling in IP-OPT. However, like in the case of three classes (Figure 4.11), the total number of applications not served correctly by the app-unaware algorithm is much higher than the applications blocked by ACINO.

Note that the number of the violated applications differs from their bandwidth. This is understandable, given that requests of 1-10Gb/s are more numerous than the 10-100Gb/s ones. The conclusion about ACINO outperforming application-unaware holds for both the number and bandwidth of the connection requests, and is more pronounced for bandwidth.

Finally, we investigate the impact of IP-OPT by omitting it from the framework completely. The results are in Table 4-10 below.

Table 4-10. Results for the realistic scenario with no IP-OPT.

IP-OPT OFF	application-unaware				ACINO			
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW
TODAY	0.7%	0.1%	5.3%	8.8%	2.1%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW
FUTURE	0.8%	0.2%	5.2%	13.9%	3.1%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%
	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW	block	block BW	SLA viol	SLA viol BW

The general conclusion about ACINO outperforming application-unaware is again valid. However, note that the number of violations for the application-unaware case is now noticeably lower, with only a small increase in blocking. This implies that IP layer optimization creates more violations. This is understandable, since IP-OPT aims to minimize blocked requests (first) and network resources (second), disregarding any violations in the app-unaware case. The extra resources made available by not optimizing can then be used to set up short paths through the network, which unintentionally satisfy the latency and the availability. The “minLat” path policy set in the parameters helps with that.

The simulations shown in figure Figure 4.12 confirm that the lower violations in the application-unaware case are at the expense of resources.

Figure 4.12. Application-unaware: IP resources for (top) and extra added IP links using OPP (bottom) needed for the IP-OPT OFF option.

In addition, the bottom plots in Figure 4.12 show that turning off IP-OPT results in less need for adding links using OPP in the today scenario. This is because extra resources are added in the beginning and there is less need to add more later. In the future scenario, the result is similar, except that in the beginning the IP-OPT

OFF option adds more resources than today, because the service requirements are more stringent. Afterwards, like today, there is a decreasing need to add more resources compared to when IP-OPT is on.

Figure 4.13 shows the situation for the ACINO case.

Figure 4.13. ACINO: IP resources for (top) and extra added IP links using OPP (bottom) needed for the IP-OPT OFF option.

With the ACINO algorithm, the small increase in blocking (as evident between Table 4-9 and Table 4-10) is the result of turning off IP-OPT. Therefore, unlike with the app-unaware case, IP-OPT is strictly beneficial in terms of resources. However, turning off IP-OPT results in less need for OPP added IP links. This implies that turning off IP-OPT saves resources but, since adding IP links (lightpaths) is relatively slow, results in a more responsive network. Note that this difference in responsiveness is more pronounced today than in the future. This we explain with the more stringent service requirements, which will in the future require adding more new lightpaths intensively even to a resource-rich (with IP_OPT off) network.

4.3.4 Overall assessment of ACINO application-aware optimization

In section 4.3 we conducted a numerical study to examine the sensitivity of our model network to the various service requirements. We then used the sensitive requirement values that can be supported by the network to evaluate the advantages of ACINO over an application-unaware algorithm. The results show that:

- ACINO uses virtually the same amount of network resources as the application-unaware strategy, but ACINO causes no SLA violations and lower to no blocking. This implies that in a real network, assuming a network topology and offered traffic similar to ours, service requirements should be accommodated with no extra investments.
- An application-unaware network incurs opportunity costs compared to ACINO. To realize this, note first that an application-unaware network causes SLA violations, which in reality may not happen because the customer would not accept a service not fitting his needs. The ACINO network can satisfy the customer needs (again, at little extra cost in resources) and charge extra for the better service. The application-aware network thus misses out on extra revenue that ACINO can generate.
- The advantage of ACINO comes at the cost of a more responsive network, where optical connections are added and removed more intensively. To enable such intensive networking, assuming connection requests arrive relatively frequently, ACINO must have an automated network orchestrator to set up and tear down optical connections, and keep track of the running services.
- A surprising result is that turning off IP layer optimization causes less SLA violations in the application-unaware case. However, this is explained by the fact that the non-optimized network has more resources. Such a network, given a reasonable effort in setting up connections, will accommodate the requested service requirements better than with IP optimization. Meanwhile, the ACINO network with IP optimization will perform better in terms of satisfying the customers, and do so with less resources compared to both the unaware network and the non-optimized ACINO. IP layer optimization thus makes sense in an application-aware setting.
- Our tools and algorithms can handle a variety of service requirements, network topologies and network equipment (transceiver types, fixed and flex-grid, etc.), so they can be exploited further. Some improvements to the algorithms are possible, too, and can be accommodated with the modular framework and code base.

Because one of the project goals of ACINO is a connection setup time of no more than 5 s, the algorithms presented here should require only a moderate amount of computation time. To get a rough upper bound on the amount of time needed to compute a path through the network, we measured the time for each simulation run on an Intel i5-based computer. In the worst case, it was 18 min 39 s for 10000 connection requests, which is, on the average 0.1 s on average for each request. This time includes, for each request, not only the time to compute the path, but also to compute and set the service requirements and its arrival and departure times. The actual time to compute a path is thus expected to be in the tens of milliseconds, which is several orders of magnitude less than the 5 s total setup time. Because our algorithms are fast,

most of the time budget can be spent on other operations in the orchestrator, or the algorithms can be modified to be slower but more exhaustive. The total connection setup time will be measured in WP 4.

4.4 Evaluation of the behaviour of fluctuating traffic demands

In this section, we extend the evaluation covered in section 4.3 by considering two further aspects related to our ACINO application-aware optimization:

- Evaluation of the behaviour of the network in presence of traffic peaks;
- Evaluation of the behaviour of the network in case of an overall increase in the network load.

While in section 4.3 the evaluation is performed by considering the today real traffic matrix provided by Telefónica (see section 6 of D2.1), in this section we want to investigate what happens if the network load fluctuates in the short-term (e.g. due to sudden events, such as sport events or natural disasters) or if, in the long-term, the overall network load increases (as widely foreseen [7]). The aim of the section is then to evaluate how the ACINO application-aware optimization faces such a network load variation. Specifically, we focus on five different performance metrics:

- *Total IP links in the network*: this metric monitors the resource occupation in terms of IP links (i.e., lightpaths and transponders).
- *Active IP links in the network*: this metric monitors the number of links that are active in the network, i.e., carry some traffic.
- *OPP added links*: this metric counts the cumulative number of IP links that have been added by the OPP module.
- *Blocking probability*: this metric evaluates the probability that a service request is blocked because it is not possible to provision it through a multi-layer path meeting all the application requirements or because of lack of resources.
- *Violation probability*: this metric evaluates the probability that a service request is provisioned by a multi-layer path that does not meet one or more application requirement and, thus, violates the SLA for such service request.

Moreover, for all the evaluations performed in this section, we consider one of the scenarios defined in section 4.3.2: we assume that the network traffic belongs to the following three traffic classes: a *latency-sensitive and reliable* class (i.e., {Latency, Availability}), a *latency-sensitive* class (i.e., {Latency}), and the *best effort* class (i.e., {Best effort}).

4.4.1 Evaluation of traffic peaks

In this section, we evaluate the behaviour of the network when it is suddenly flooded by some traffic for a limited amount of time: we consider a traffic peak that lasts for 1/4 of the simulation time. First, we compare the behaviour of our *ACINO (optimized) application-aware* (*ACINO* in short) and the multi-layer *non-application aware* (*AppUnaware* in short) approaches presented in section 4.1.3. Then, we focus on

the ACINO approach and we consider multiple scenarios in terms of *i)* different percentages of application-aware traffic classes and *ii)* different amplitudes for the traffic peak.

Comparison between ACINO and AppUnaware approaches

To perform a comparison between the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches we assume that 20% of the network traffic is latency-sensitive and reliable, 20% is latency-sensitive, and 60% is best effort. This means that 40% of the overall traffic is application-aware, i.e., it requires that some application requirements are met (otherwise SLAs would be violated). We also assume a 2x factor for the network traffic when the peak occurs, i.e., the network load is doubled in the peak time-window. Even though simulating a sudden and short-term doubling in the network traffic may be unrealistic, such an amplitude allows to strongly stress it and to provide some interesting insights on its reactivity in case of traffic fluctuations.

Before starting our evaluation, it is worth recalling that the removal frequency of idle IP links after an ACINO or multi-layer optimization (see section 4.1.3) is a useful parameter for tuning the balance between energy consumption and time responsiveness of the network. In fact, a low removal frequency of idle IP links increases the time responsiveness of the network, since such links can be used by new service requests without the need of setting up new lightpaths. On the other hand, a low removal frequency risks to increase the overall energy consumption, since the transponders for the idle IP links that must be kept powered on even though those links do not carry traffic. Moreover, in our framework the IP links can be removed *i)* after a certain number of IP-OPT calls (i.e., after a certain number of IPP fails) or *ii)* after a certain number of IPP successes.

Figure 4.14: Number of active IP links in the network for both the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches.

Concerning this aspect, Figure 4.14 shows the number of active IP links as a function of the simulation time for both the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches. The simulation stops after the provisioning of 10000 service requests. The green area of the graph underlines when the peak occurs. It can be seen how the number of active IP links increases of about 75% for both ACINO and AppUnaware. This means that during the peak more lightpaths need to be established to accommodate the more and more service requests arriving in the network. However, there is no major deviation in the number of active IP links between the two approaches, proving that the ACINO approach does not consumes more resources than the

AppUnaware, while offering application-awareness even in case of traffic peaks. Moreover, both approaches make the network very responsive and able to provision service requests on a minimum number of needed IP links, by avoiding fragmentation of resources. This is well shown in the Figure, since the number of active IP links suddenly decreases when the network traffic starts decreasing after the peak.

Figure 4.15 and Figure 4.16 focus on the total number of IP links in the network (including the idle IP links) as a function of the simulation time, while adopting different policies for the removal of idle IP links. In Figure 4.15, the idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls, while in Figure 4.16 the idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP successes. These two policies lead to very different results in terms of number of total IP links in the network over time.

Figure 4.15 shows that only removing IP links every 10 IP-OPT calls may be inefficient when a peak occurs. In fact, at the end of the traffic peak, the total number of IP links does not immediately follow the traffic decrease, but remains constant for a certain amount of time. At a certain point, all the idle IP links are removed and the network starts following the traffic again. This is especially true for the AppUnaware approach, while the ACINO approach has a better reactivity. The reason behind this behaviour is that the probability of calling IP-OPT and, thus, of failing IPP, is higher in the ACINO than in the AppUnaware approach. This is not surprising, since the ACINO approach meets multiple application requirements and finding an application-aware path is in general harder than just selecting an application-unaware path, especially by re-using existing resources in the IP layer. When the traffic starts decreasing at the end of the peak, the bandwidth reserved for many service requests starts being released and many IP links become idle. In the AppUnaware approach, such IP links are more easily re-used for the IP provisioning of new connections (by successfully calling IPP), and thus idle IP links are not removed for a longer time, since IP-OPT is unlikely to be called. When IP-OPT is called for 10 consecutive times, all the idle IP links are removed simultaneously (shown as breaks in the curve). In the ACINO approach, idle IP links are instead removed more frequently, since IP-OPT is called much more frequently. This means that the adoption as policy of removing idle IP links after 10 IP-OPT calls is not good from an energy consumption perspective, especially if traffic peaks are envisioned.

Figure 4.15: Number of total IP links in the network for both the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls.

Decreasing the removal frequency by reducing the number of IP-OPT calls after which the idle IP links removal occurs (e.g. 5, or 2) mitigates this effect. If using an extreme solution, i.e., if IP links are removed every 1 IP-OPT call, the network closely follows the traffic also during the peak, and the curves showing the number of total IP links in the network closely match the curves related to the number of active IP links. However, in this way the responsiveness of the network is reduced, since the failing of IPP and IP-OPT is more likely to happen, much more IP links need to be added by OPP and setting up new lightpaths requires up to a few minutes. We do not report graphs on such experiments for the sake of conciseness.

An alternative strategy can be adopted to make the network closely follow the traffic, also in presence of peaks, without lowering too much its responsiveness. The idea is to consider a policy in which, other than removing the idle IP links after 10 IP-OPT calls, they are removed also after 50 IPP successful calls. In this way, as Figure 4.16 shows, both the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches allow to remove idle IP links more frequently to save energy consumption. Clearly, the more the frequency removal after IPP success is reduced (e.g. 30, 20 or 10), the more the curves showing the number of total IP links closely match the curves showing the number of active IP links.

Figure 4.16: Number of total IP links in the network for both the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success.

We now focus on the evaluation of the OPP added links metric. Figure 4.17 shows the number of cumulative OPP added links over time for both the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches. First, we can see that the slope for the ACINO curve is higher than for the AppUnaware one, since the ACINO approach fails IPP more often than the AppUnaware and requires a more dynamic provisioning of optical resources, as explained above. Moreover, when the peak occurs, we can see that the slope of the curves changes for both ACINO and AppUnaware approaches. At the beginning, a higher slope is experienced, since new IP links need to be added by OPP at a higher pace to provision the high number of service requests flooding the network. When the peak is finishing, the slope of the curves decreases for a while, meaning that in that phase the traffic load decreases and idle IP links can be re-used for new service requests.

Figure 4.17: Number of OPP added links in the network for both the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success.

Finally, we focus on blocking and SLA violation probability. For this kind of evaluation, we consider the provisioning of 50000 service requests and we average the results over 50 different rounds, to increase the statistical confidence, since we are dealing with very small numbers. We compare the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches when the network experiences a peak or not. Results are shown in Table 4.11. First, we can see that ACINO does not violate any SLA, while the SLA violation probability for the AppUnaware is around 6%. This proves the effectiveness of the ACINO approach in providing application-aware paths to the service requests. Moreover, the ACINO approach leads to some blocking probability, while AppUnaware does not. The reason behind this behaviour is that in ACINO the service requests not meeting SLAs are a priori blocked, while in AppUnaware they are not. Table 4.11 also shows how in ACINO the blocking probability is higher in presence of a peak, meaning that during the peak it is harder to find an application-aware path for the service requests because of a higher occupation of resources. Similar results are obtained for SLA violation probability in case of AppUnaware, i.e., in case of peaks there is a higher probability of SLA violations.

Table 4.11: Blocking and SLA violation probability for both the ACINO and the AppUnaware approaches with and without traffic peaks.

	ACINO		AppUnaware	
	Blocking	SLA Violation	Blocking	SLA Violation
With peak	3.16E-05	0	0	6.23E-02
Without peak	1.48E-05	0	0	6.12E-02

Variation in the percentage of application-aware classes and in the amplitude of the peak

We now focus on the ACINO optimized application-aware approach, and investigate what happens *i)* when the network traffic changes its composition and *ii)* when the peaks have different amplitudes.

Figure 4.18 shows the number of total IP links in the network when three different application-aware classes percentages and a 2x network traffic factor during the peak are considered. The percentage of application-aware traffic (e.g. 10%) is equally split between the *latency-sensitive* (i.e., {Latency}) class (5%) and the *latency-sensitive and reliable* (i.e., {Latency, Availability}) class (5%). The same happens with 40% (20% latency-sensitive and 20% latency-sensitive and reliable) and with 90% (45% latency-sensitive and 45% latency-sensitive and reliable). The remaining percentage of traffic, in every case, is *best-effort* traffic. By increasing the percentage of application-aware traffic, we simulate a scenario in which the application-aware traffic will become dominant, since more and more applications, in the future, will ask for very stringent service requirements. As Figure 4.18 shows, the total number of IP links does not strongly depend on the traffic composition, not even during the peak. This is true if the average bandwidth occupation for a service request is the same for any traffic class, as assumed in this scenario.

Figure 4.18: Number of total IP links in the network for the ACINO approach, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success, when different percentages of application-aware traffic are considered (10%, 40%, 90%) and with 2x network traffic during the peak.

In Table 4.12, we show the blocking and SLA violation probability for the ACINO approach, with and without a traffic peak. By increasing the percentage of application-aware traffic we can see how, on the one hand, the blocking probability slightly increases both with and without a traffic peak. This happens because in case of higher application-aware traffic percentages some connections may not find an application-aware path due to lack of resources (e.g. a higher number of latency-sensitive service requests in the network means that more requests must be necessarily routed on the shortest paths, that may become busy). In addition, the blocking probability is slightly higher in case of traffic peaks, as already explained in Table 4.11.

Moreover, as expected, the ACINO approach never leads to SLA violations. These results confirm that the ACINO approach is beneficial also when jointly *i)* there is an increase in the application-aware traffic in the network and *ii)* sudden traffic peaks occur. In fact, no SLA violation as well as only a marginal increase in the blocking probability is experienced.

Table 4.12: Blocking and SLA violation probability for the ACINO approach in case of different percentages of application-aware traffic, with 2x traffic peak and without peak.

Percentage	With peak		Without peak	
	Blocking	SLA Violation	Blocking	SLA Violation
10%	3.27E-06	0	2.00E-06	0
40%	3.16E-05	0	1.48E-05	0
90%	8.32E-05	0	5.52E-05	0

We now consider, in our evaluation, the impact of different amplitudes for the traffic peak. Figure 4.19 shows the number of total IP links in the network when four different amplitudes for the peak are considered: 1.25x (i.e., 25% more traffic during the peak), 1.5x, 1.75x and 2x. The percentage of application-aware traffic is 40%. The Figure shows that an increase in the traffic during the peak leads to an increase in the number of total IP links in the network. Specifically, with a 1.25x factor there are around 20% more total IP links during the peak, with a factor 1.5x around 35%, with a factor 1.75x around 50% and with a factor 2x around 75%. The increase in the number of IP links during the peak is consistently lower than the increase in the traffic (e.g. when the traffic doubles, we have only 75% more IP links) since the ACINO approach, in case of sudden load increase, can groom traffic in an effective way on already-existing IP links thanks to IPP (if the application requirements are met) before requiring the provisioning of new optical resources (through OPP).

Figure 4.19: Number of total IP links in the network for the ACINO approach, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success, when different amplitudes for the traffic peak are considered (1.25x, 1.5x, 1.75x, 2x) and with 40% of application-aware traffic.

In Table 4.13, we finally show the blocking and SLA violation probability for the ACINO approach. As experienced before, the ACINO approach is inherently designed to never violate SLAs. Conversely, we can see that by increasing the peak amplitude the blocking probability increases accordingly. Specifically, no

more blocking is experienced in case of 1.25x amplitude for the peak with respect to the *no peak* case, meaning that if there is up to a 25% increase in the traffic during the peak, the network can provision the service requests as if there was not any peak. The blocking probability instead increases when the peak amplitude further increases, since during the peak period it becomes harder and harder to find an application-aware path for the increasing number of application-aware service requests flooding the network.

Table 4.13 Blocking and SLA violation probability for the ACINO approach in case of different peak amplitudes and with 40% of application-aware traffic.

Peak amplitude	Blocking	SLA Violation
No peak	1.48E-05	0
1.25x	1.48E-05	0
1.5x	1.84E-05	0
1.75x	1.96E-05	0
2x	3.16E-05	0

4.4.2 Evaluation of overall increasing load

To conclude our evaluation, we investigate how the network reacts to a long-term increase in the network load, i.e., if the overall network traffic increases by a certain factor with respect to the traffic experienced today by Telefónica. We refer to the today traffic as *1x*, and we increase the network load up to a factor of *8x*, i.e., up to 8 times the current load. The percentage of application-aware traffic is 40%.

Figure 4.20: Number of total IP links in the network for the ACINO approach, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success, when different network loads are considered (1x, 2x, 4x, 6x, 8x) and with 40% of application-aware traffic.

Figure 4.20 shows the number of total IP links in the network for different traffic loads. The total number of IP links increases as the traffic load increases and reaches a steady state. For example, when an 8x factor for the traffic load is considered, the number of total IP links is around 6 times greater (once the steady state is reached). Since the increase factor in the number of total IP links is lower than the load scale factor, this means that the ACINO approach can effectively face an overall load increase by effectively grooming

the service requests on already-existing IP links and by adding new IP links through OPP only when needed (i.e., when an application-aware path cannot be found by IPP).

Figure 4.21 shows instead the number of cumulative OPP added links for the different traffic loads. The number of cumulative OPP added links is higher for higher traffic loads, since more IP links are needed in the network to provision a higher number of service requests (as also confirmed by Figure 4.20). Moreover, an increase in the network load makes the network more dynamic, since it should turn on and switch off IP links more frequently. This behaviour supports the idea that adopting a centralized orchestrator as the one envisioned by ACINO will become of paramount importance for the management of more loaded and dynamic application-aware networks.

Figure 4.21: Number of OPP added links in the network for the ACINO approach, when idle IP links are removed every 10 IP-OPT calls and every 50 IPP success, when different network loads are considered (1x, 2x, 4x, 6x, 8x) and with 40% of application-aware traffic.

Finally, in Table 4.14 we show the blocking and SLA violation probability. We focus our attention on both the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches. As usual, no SLA violation probability is experienced by ACINO, while AppUnaware leads to around 6% of SLA violations. It is noteworthy that the blocking probability for ACINO consistently increases when the load scale factor increases. This happens because if the overall network load increases it is harder *i)* to find application-aware paths for application-aware traffic and *ii)* to find paths with available bandwidth for both application-aware and best effort traffic (i.e., there is a lack of physical resources). The latter aspect is also well shown by looking at the blocking probability for AppUnaware: for load scale factors greater than 4x, AppUnaware experiences some blocking. Such blocking can only be caused by a lack of physical resources, since AppUnaware does not block any SLA-violating path. If we look at the SLA violation for AppUnaware, we can see that it slightly grows when the load scale factor increases. In fact, an increase in the network load makes the shortest paths busy and makes AppUnaware start provisioning service requests on longer paths, also for application-aware traffic that would require short paths (e.g. latency-sensitive traffic). Such an inefficient provisioning leads to higher

violations, since AppUnaware provisions application-aware and best effort service requests in the same way.

Table 4.14: Blocking and SLA violation probability for the ACINO and AppUnaware approaches in case of different traffic loads and with 40% of application-aware traffic.

Load scale factor	ACINO		AppUnaware	
	Blocking	SLA Violation	Blocking	SLA Violation
1x	1.48E-05	0	0	6.12E-02
2x	1.21E-04	0	0	6.33E-02
4x	1.94E-04	0	0	6.59E-02
6x	4.12E-04	0	3.42E-04	6.73E-02
8x	1.63E-02	0	1.85E-02	9.06E-02

5 Offline operation and features

While offline operations are strictly not part of Task 3.4, we present here a use of our tool in situations where the network operator wants to explore certain possibilities described below. The general goal is to predict the behaviour of the network before the simulated events occur, and then, as needed, take appropriate actions to prepare the network for the events.

We first describe the simulation platform, then the scenarios, and finally describe the use of the tool with the scenarios with concrete examples.

5.1 Description of the offline ACINO Net2Plan simulation platform

The Net2Plan version enhanced by ACINO can be used offline as well as online: the same code and tools as for the online simulation are used, and its user interface can be manipulated to tune the relevant parameters to simulate the situation of interest. Therefore, to carry out the examples below, no changes are necessary. However, to support a larger variety of scenarios, some of which are discussed below, the code should be enhanced. We leave this for future work.

5.2 Supported and possible what-if scenarios

The scenarios involve two different situations. The first is inserting connection requests that are not or cannot be easily simulated with the traffic generator described in section 3.2. This can be an exceptionally large (in Gb/s) request, or a particularly constrained (with other service requirements) one, or one that does not fit in the specified traffic classes. To generalize, the user can insert multiple connection requests at one time, and use the tool to observe if and how these requests are accommodated by the network. To generalize even further, the user can run the simulation with particular traffic, change the traffic input, and continue running. However, the last generalization is not possible with the current code, so we leave the necessary code modifications for future work. The second scenario is a network component failure, such as an IP port failure or a fibre-link cut.

5.2.1 Inserting a new connection requests

Accommodating with IP-OPT

In this case, it is assumed that the network operator can change only the IP layer to accommodate the connection requests. This has the advantage of being faster to implement in the network, and reduces the chance of failed lightpath setups causing service interruptions to the running services. We thus use only the IP-OPT to accommodate the new requests.

Accommodating with the entire ACINO framework

Instead of using only IP-OPT, the hypothetical connection request is accommodated in this scenario with the entire framework. However, the current code for IPP and OPP only supports accommodating one connection request at a time. In order to accommodate multiple requests, the user can insert one request, accommodate it, and start anew with the next request.

5.2.2 Network failures accommodated with IP-OPT

After a failure, there will be one or more disrupted services. Using IP-OPT, the network recovers as many

services as possible in the IP layer. In other words, optical restoration is not simulated. It should be noted that restoring a service in the IP layer alone is faster than restoring optical connections.

We can simulate a failure of one or more IP links. The cause may be an IP port failure, which will disconnect one IP link and disrupt zero, one or more IP connections traversing the link. If a fibre-link was cut instead, multiple IP links may fail. However, the current code cannot simulate this automatically. Instead, the user can manually fail the IP links that would be affected in reality. For each fibre-link, the associated IP links can be found in the tool, and the IP links can then be set as failed.

5.3 What-if scenario examples

This subsection demonstrates how to accommodate a new, hypothetical, connection request first, then how to test the network behaviour after a failure.

Accommodating a new connection request

We first run an online simulation as in section 4. For the purpose of this test, we run a 2-class case where the sensitive class requires a 6ms latency. The result is shown in Figure 5.1. The IP layer shown in the figure was created by running a simulation with 5000 connection requests. Next, using the GUI we insert two demands of 14 Gb/s with a 6 ms latency. These requests (called Demands in Net2Plan) have no routes yet.

Figure 5.1. New connection requests inserted using the GUI (highlighted red).

Next, we run IP-OPT by selecting the Algorithm execution tab and loading the Java class file. The algorithm runs for less than a second and produces the result shown below in Figure 5.2. IP-OPT found a route for both requests and the services are running. This means that, if the two requests arrived after the simulated 10000 requests, they could be accommodated by the network, so the network operator does not need to upgrade the network to accommodate them.

Figure 5.2. The user-inserted requests are accommodated and highlighted green.

Accommodating a failure

First, in the GUI we fail a single IP link, highlighted in red in Figure 5.3 below. The IP layer shown in the figure was created by running a simulation with 5000 connection requests.

Figure 5.3. Model network IP layer and a failed IP link.

Figure 5.4 shows the three affected IP connections, i.e. the affected services.

Figure 5.4. The affected IP connections are highlighted in red in the GUI. One is selected by the user so it is highlighted in blue on the right, and its route is red in the topology view.

Next, IP-OPT run by selecting the Algorithm execution tab and loading the Java class file. The execution takes less than a second. The result is shown Figure 5.5, where a new route in the IP layer was found for two of the three affected IP connections. The network operator now knows which services will suffer an interruption after the failure of the selected IP link, and can take measures to prepare for the failure.

Figure 5.5. The repaired services are marked green, and the one unrepaired IP connection is still highlighted red.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AG	Auxiliary Graph
BW	Bandwidth
CLI	Command Line Interface
FF	First Fit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IP	Internet Protocol
IP-OPT	IP (Layer) Optimization
IPP	IP provision
LSP	Label Switched Path
ML	Multi-Layer
ML-OPT	Multi-Layer Optimization
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
OPP	Optical provision
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SP	Shortest Path
WDM	Wavelength Division Multiplexing
WP	Work Package

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